

ARGOS

Conceptual Design Study

Designing a Next-Generation Radio Facility for Multi-Messenger Astronomy

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Author: **Antonios Makrogiannakis (FORTH)**
Stefanos Papadakis (FORTH)

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Table of Contents

DOCUMENT HISTORY 2

PEER REVIEW HISTORY..... 2

RELEASE HISTORY 2

DISCLAIMER 2

1. INTRODUCTION 5

PURPOSE & SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT 5

CONTENT OF THE DOCUMENT 5

2. OVERVIEW OF EXISTING SYSTEMS & PLATFORMS..... 5

3. HIGH-LEVEL ARCHITECTURE 6

HIGH-LEVEL DESCRIPTION 6

SERVICES ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW 8

SERVICES ARCHITECTURE COMPONENTS 9

Storage module/database 9

Data ingest module 9

Cross-matching module 9

Filtering module..... 9

Alert broker queues 9

Real-time algorithms 10

Non real-time algorithms 10

User Interface module 10

4. VIRTUALIZATION ARCHITECTURE 10

VIRTUALIZATION 11

LOAD BALANCING 12

REDUNDANCY / AVAILABILITY 12

SCALABILITY 12

MONITORING 13

5. HARDWARE INFRASTRUCTURE 13

COMPUTING NODES/FABRIC..... 14

NETWORKING NODES/FABRIC 14

STORAGE NODES/FABRIC 14

6. PROVISION FOR DATA SPACES..... 15

7. CONCLUSIONS 16

8. REFERENCES 16

List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Description
COTS	Commercial off-the-shelf
GbE	Gigabit Ethernet
NIC	Network Interface Controller
Gbps	Gigabit per second
CPU	Central Processing Unit
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
SPEAD	Streaming Protocol for Exchange of Astronomy Data
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
WP	Work Package
VO	Virtual Observatory
ADC	Analog to Digital Converter
VM	Virtual Machine
SDN	Software Defined Network
LXC	LinuX Containers
NUMA	Non-uniform memory access
HCI	Hyper-converged infrastructure
SSD	Solid State Disk
NVMe	Non-Volatile Memory Express (Host Controller Interface Specification)
NGSI	Next Generation Service Interfaces

1. Introduction

Purpose & Scope of the document

The purpose of this document is to describe in detail the architecture of the Archiving and Alerts subsystem of the ARGOS system. It provides a vertical view of all the software and hardware components needed and their respective structure, in order to build a robust and scalable system that can cope with the requirements of ARGOS and also be capable to serve the produced data to the community efficiently and in a timely fashion.

Content of the document

The document is organized as follows: In Section 2 an overview of the existing systems and technologies is presented, in Section 3 the high-level architecture of ARGOS' respective subsystem and its components are depicted, in Section 4 the virtualization architecture that supports the services and functionalities offered by the archiving and alerts subsystem is described, in Section 5 the specifications and components of the required hardware infrastructure are provided, and last in Section 6 the data spaces provisioning is introduced.

2. Overview of existing systems & platforms

Modern astronomical observations produce a vast amount of data that must not only be stored but also be made accessible and interoperable so as to be useful to the global research community. Robust archiving systems for astronomical data, equipped with cross-matching collaborative capabilities and open to the scientific community, are necessary and indispensable and require the proper attention in their design and development.

There are numerous sophisticated and comprehensive astrophysics archiving systems that have the ability to (a) manage large volumes of data, (b) quickly adapt to new discoveries, and (c) facilitate effective collaboration.

The European Southern Observatory (ESO) Science Archive Facility and the Canadian Initiative for Radio Astronomy Data Analysis (CIRADA), hosted by the Canadian Astronomy Data Centre (CADDC) are two state-of-the-art modern archiving systems. They typically collect raw data from several telescopes and other astronomical instruments around the globe. The ESO Science Archive Facility contains data from ESO telescopes at La Silla and Paranal Observatories, as well as the APEX sub-millimeter telescope on Llano de Chajnantor, and the UK Infrared Telescope facility in Hawaii. CIRADA hosts data from Canadian Hydrogen Intensity Mapping Experiment (CHIME) and the Very Large Array Sky Survey (VLASS). Raw observational data undergo a series of operations by automated pipelines running in their highly available and powerful computing infrastructure in order to provide science-ready data products. At first, the obtained raw data are processed and calibrated accordingly to compensate for instrumental and atmospheric effects. Calibration of the raw data is a crucial operation that ensures that the data acquired depict accurately the observed astronomical event. After the step of calibration, advanced algorithms are applied to the calibrated data for various types of data analysis such as image or spectral line analysis to produce high-quality data-sets. The sum of the produced data-sets and meta-data, which include details for observational parameters, e.g., observation times and conditions, and processing procedures, are securely stored in the high-performance and scalable disk storage infrastructure of these archiving systems. Finally, data access is granted to anyone in the scientific or enthusiast community through user-friendly web interfaces while Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) allow users to programmatically incorporate data query, discovery, and retrieval in their own software.

The availability of astronomical data archiving systems led to the conception of virtual observatories (VOs). A virtual observatory's main goal is to provide astronomical data from various real telescopes and archiving

systems allowing astronomers across the globe to interrogate multiple data centers in a transparent and seamless way. To achieve this and to ensure interoperability, standardization of data types and format, and exchange communication protocols is essential to normalize different heterogeneous observation collections from different scientific instruments managed by various national and international astronomical data centers. The Virtual Astronomical Observatory (VAO), the U.S. NSF- and NASA-funded VO effort, is one of the state-of-the-art virtual observatories bringing a large-scale electronic integration of astronomy data, tools, and services to the global community.

Although these systems provide the community with a vast amount of rich astronomical data, deep in their core, they are large databases with a fixed set of data that astronomers have to discover by themselves and perform the appropriate queries to obtain corresponding data for an event. The rise of transient astronomy led to the need for astronomers to be notified about an event of interest in real time as it is happening or after only a short delay. This incentive created the world of astronomical data streaming. Modern systems extend the idea of astronomical data archiving to astronomical data streaming which involve real-time processing of data for alert generation, real-time annotation and classification of alerts. The most modern example of this type of alerting system is created by the Zwicky Transient Facility (ZTF) [1] which uses the Samuel Oschin Telescope at the Palomar Observatory in California, United States. The Zwicky Transient Facility Alert Distribution System (ZADS) [2] generates real-time alerts for optical transient objects and moving objects discovered in its wide-field survey. The aforementioned alerts are filtered with specific reduction algorithms and stored in the high-throughput storage infrastructure of ZTF while delivering them to full stream alert brokers. These alert brokers cross-match with other catalogs and alert streams, classify events, redistribute alert packets to other downstream brokers and disseminate alerts to interested science users in a publish/subscribe manner. Various community brokers have been developed throughout the years like ALerCE [3], Lasair and ANTARES [4] and are fully accessible to the scientific community and the public in general.

3. High-level architecture

In this section the high-level architecture of the archiving and alerting subsystem of ARGOS is described.

High-level description

In Figure 1 a high-level overview of the ARGOS components is presented. The real-time processing of the E/M spectrum captured by the antennas may produce bursts of high-volume data, both raw and processed, along with alerts of specific phenomena detections, at the end of the processing chain.

Figure 1: High-level overview of ARGOS-CDS

Therefore, a robust and scalable system should be built in order to handle these bursts of data, without missing any, even under stressful, high repetition rate events. Moreover, it should be able to provide real-time alerting and high-volume data transfers to the community for further investigations.

In order to better depict the architecture and describe the details of the archiving and alerting software system a three-layer design is shown in Figure 2. The Services layer corresponds to all the services and functionalities of the system, the Virtualization layer provides the abstraction and robustness of the system, and the Hardware Infrastructure layer represents the computing and networking nodes and their inter-connectivity.

Figure 2: The three layers of logical separation

In the present section the top layer will be described in detail and the other two crucial supporting layers are presented in the next two sections.

Services Architecture overview

In this section we describe in detail the system architecture and design of the archiving and alerting software subsystem of ARGOS project. In Figure 3 we provide the system architecture, the components and how they connect and communicate with each other to implement a platform for storing and streaming ARGOS observational data and alerts.

Figure 3: The Archiving and Alerting Subsystem architecture

This subsystem is primarily responsible for ingesting data and metadata from the science pipelines (WP6 and WP7). These data may be of various types such as images, waveforms, raw channelized voltages from the RF Backend and alerts, depending on the type of the event that is observed. The received data are securely stored in the subsystem archive, tagged and grouped together based on the observed event. Next, different observations from the same event are gathered and correlated by querying other publicly available archives and catalogs cross-matching the event. Later steps involve two processing queues, a real-time and a non-real-time one, that are initiated almost at the same time for the same set of event and alert data that were stored in the previous step. The real-time queue encompasses software modules that run fast and light-weight computation algorithms for stamp classification and filtering while generating alerts ready for consumption by science users. The system gives us the option to store or discard the output results of the aforementioned procedure. The non-real-time queue involves software modules that are entitled to run heavy-duty algorithms producing more useful data-sets about an event and/or observation. These data-sets are stored appropriately

with specific tags that represent the specific observed event, in question for later acquisition and study from the community.

Services Architecture Components

In this subsection we provide a more detailed overview of the system components that are combined and work together to compose the overall system architecture of the archiving and alerting system of ARGOS.

Storage module/database

The storage module of the system is the heart of the ARGOS archiving capabilities as far as storage is concerned. It embodies the deployment of a large-scale, high-availability, scalable, distributed and clustered relational database. We choose PostgreSQL as the best one of the candidates for the role of the database because of its rich capabilities in terms of modes of operation. A multi-master replicated cluster is considered where replication lets multiple nodes accept write queries and all of the nodes involved contain the same data. Every master accepts read and writes operations and when the primary server fails it is not necessary to wait for a physical standby to be promoted. The database archive is partitioned in three main categories, alerts, data and computed data where the very same alert, the raw data and meta-data and the non-real time future computed data-sets for events are accommodated respectively. Alerts, data and meta-data for a specific event are characterized by a unique identifier and grouped together for future retrieval and correlation.

Data ingest module

The data ingest module is responsible for acquiring events alerts and data from the Science Pipelines that run in the backend of the ARGOS system. It inherently shares a common filesystem with the Science Pipelines' software for easy monitoring and data transfer between them. When an event occurs and all alerts and data are written in the filesystem, the data ingest module is notified and immediately starts reading them while efficiently storing them in the aforementioned Storage module/database.

Cross-matching module

The main objective of the cross-matching module, as its name suggests, is to compare the event data that was observed by the ARGOS platform with other data-sets for the same event from other telescopes and observatories. It searches other publicly available catalogs, archives or alert streams trying to correlate data using advanced cross-matching techniques such as Positional Cross-Matching, Temporal Cross-Matching or Multi-Wavelength Data Matching. Upon successful cross-matching, meta-data from other sources are also embedded in our already recorded data.

Filtering module

The filtering module encompasses software components that run filtering techniques for the events observed from ARGOS. In more detail, this module applies predefined filters on the stream of the observed events for a number of predefined science use cases. Each filter creates a stream of events of the same type and associates them with a topic in Kafka [5] stream queues, discussed below. The above process can be also augmented by the use of user-defined filters allowing users to develop filtering code by following platform guidelines.

Alert broker queues

Alert broker queues are the system components responsible for delivering alerts to the scientific community and interested end-users in general. A scalable cluster of highly available Apache Kafka instances is utilized to meet the high performance and reliability requirements of the system. Apache Kafka is an open-source stream-processing software platform aiming to provide a unified, high-throughput, low-latency platform for handling real-time data feeds. Kafka acts as a broker between producers, ARGOS alerting subsystem pipelines and consumers, and the science end-users. Instead of using the standardized VOEvent format over VTP (VOEvent Transport Protocol), we choose to utilize the newly proposed combination of Apache Kafka and Avro format to describe alert events. Alerts are partitioned according to the filtering codes discussed

earlier and sent to specific Kafka queues associated with unique topics. Eligible consumers subscribe to topics through Apache Kafka interfaces enabling them to reliably retrieve filtered alert streams according to their needs. Possible extension of the alerting system can be achieved by connecting publicly available community downstream alert brokers, like ALeRCE, ANTARES or Comet [7], to distribute ARGOS alert stream to a wider audience while saving computational resources. While ALeRCE and ANTARES integration can be easily achieved, as they support the combination of Kafka/Avro natively, Comet integration could be more challenging because it is based on the VTP/VOEvent technology.

Real-time algorithms

This component involves software components that run fast, and low complexity “light” algorithms, which require minimal computing resources, on the alerts and data received before sending them to the filtering module. Various pre-processing and classification techniques are applied here with the prerequisite that they do not have severe impact on the alert distribution delay. Therefore, modules that are able to consume the data they are receiving in higher rate than the expected incoming rate, are considered real-time.

Non real-time algorithms

This component runs in the non-real time queue applying heavy-duty algorithms on event data producing rich data-sets that may be available after a longer period of time. The quality of these data-sets is enhanced when more and more complicated scientific algorithms are applied on them asynchronously in the background. The relevant computed data for events are stored along with other data and meta-data from previous pipelines in the storage module/database characterized by unique event identifiers. Science users are informed from the user interface what type of algorithms are running or finished and are encouraged to query our platform for further results at a later time.

User Interface module

ARGOS users interact with the alerting and archiving system using a Web-based User Interface. Using a web interface offers several benefits, such as platform independence, ease of access and security, making it a popular choice for interacting with various applications and services. In more detail, the User Interface module combines the power of Python, Node.js and React Javascript library to build a robust and scalable application. Python excels in areas such as data analysis, scientific computing and backend development while Node.js provides a non-blocking, event-driven architecture, making it suitable for building richful Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). We build our frontend interface on React which is ideal for developing interactive and responsive frontend applications.

4. Virtualization Architecture

A system’s quality is characterized by the following desirable traits: stability, high availability, data and software redundancy, and zero downtime. In order to achieve a system with these traits, the infrastructure must employ load-balancing, auto-scaling, fail-over and self-monitoring techniques, eliminating possible single points of failure that would degrade the quality of the system and consequently of the services provided.

Focusing on the system requirements described above, we opt for a distributed and virtualized architecture depicted in Figure 4 and adopt it for the hierarchical architecture design of the platform that will host all of the software components and data.

Figure 4: The Virtualization architecture

Virtualization

Generally, building a system with multi-purpose heterogeneous services running either synchronously or asynchronously, isolated or interconnected, on a well-defined infrastructure with specific resources can be quite challenging. The key for addressing the challenges that may arise is the deployment of virtualization environments as it is the most modern and robust approach when designing large-scale complex systems. Virtualization is the act of creating a virtual (rather than actual) version of something at the same abstraction level, including virtual computer hardware platforms, storage devices, and computer network resources. Virtualization enables the creation of multiple simulated environments or dedicated resources from a single physical hardware system. Virtualization provides resource efficiency, isolation and security, flexibility and scalability, disaster recovery and high availability and simplified management and automation. There are several virtualization types, but in our services architecture design we shall extensively use full hardware virtualization and operating system virtualization usually known as containerization. Full hardware virtualization is a complete simulation of the actual hardware to allow software environments, including a guest operating system and its apps, to run unmodified whereas containerization is OS-level virtualization to run multiple isolated user-space instances (containers) on a single OS kernel. For deploying Virtual Machines (VMs), we shall benefit from the use of bare-metal hypervisors such as Proxmox (KVM-based) that runs directly on the physical hardware. In the very same isolated Virtual Machines, we may use containerization techniques such as Docker, LXC or containers managed by Kubernetes. Kubernetes is an orchestration platform for managing containerized distributed applications at scale which involves the clustering of several nodes collaborating with each other. In general, the majority of our system services and applications (typically deployed with Helm Charts and Kustomize) should run inside a Kubernetes cluster of virtualized nodes on several physical Proxmox nodes on ARGOS premises. Kubernetes is a key feature in ARGOS deployment because it contributes to all the system requirements as we discuss in the next subsections.

Load Balancing

The system is required to respond in an efficient and quick manner dealing with situations of high demand and heavy load. Service load-balancing techniques are incorporated to enhance performance, reliability, and availability. Load-balancers assist in efficient traffic distribution, reduced latency and enhanced throughput. They distribute incoming network or application traffic across multiple servers, ensuring no single server becomes overwhelmed while they reduce response time and latency, leading to a better user experience. As we discussed earlier, our system services shall run on a Kubernetes cluster which already provides several mechanisms for load balancing to ensure that application traffic is efficiently distributed across the various components and services in a cluster. In front of these internal services, we deploy external load-balancers to route external network traffic in a much more sophisticated way. Each type of internal service, that may consist of multiple of containers running on Kubernetes is assigned one load-balancer which performs regular health checks on the status and the health of the underlying services. The proper configuration of the load-balancers, on how they respond in case of failures, is crucial for the stability of the system. Additionally, we deploy reverse proxies in front of the load-balancers to act as intermediaries for requests from clients seeking resources from other servers. These reverse proxies are used to manage inbound traffic to internal servers and deal with use cases of caching, SSL termination, and security enhancement in general.

Redundancy / Availability

Primarily, deploying a cluster of multiple nodes running bare-metal hypervisors (e.g., Proxmox) for managing Virtual Machines, networking and storage, ensures redundancy and availability of virtualized environments. Redundancy and availability refer to having multiple components that perform the same function, in case one component fails, other can take over, in order the system to remain operational and accessible. Running a well configured cluster with abundance of nodes ensures that Virtual Machines and containers remain operational even in the event of hardware or software failures. In case of a node failure, Virtual Machines and containers can be automatically migrated to another node in the cluster. This ensures that services remain available even if a physical server goes down. Moreover, a cluster of hypervisors can automatically detect node failures and initiate fail-over procedures to restart VMs/containers on other nodes within the cluster. There is also a second level of redundancy and availability in our system as far as application services are concerned. As mentioned earlier, we opted for Kubernetes which is designed to ensure high availability and redundancy, that are critical for running production-grade applications. Kubernetes ensures that a specified number of application replicas are running at all times. If an application replica fails, Kubernetes will automatically start a new one to maintain the desired state. This replica can be scheduled on any available node, providing redundancy if a node fails. In this fashion, we maintain a two-level architecture of redundancy and availability, in case of either hardware or software failures.

Scalability

Scalability refers to the ability to increase the capacity and performance of a system by adding or upgrading hardware or software components and it is a critical aspect of system design and infrastructure management in computing. It can allow for growth accommodation ensuring that the system can handle increased load without degradation in performance as an application or service gains either more users or its computing resources requirements increase. Scalability assists in improved performance and maintaining performance levels, ensuring a consistent and reliable user experience even as usage increases and also helps in distributing the load across multiple servers or nodes, reducing the latency and improving response times. Our architectural approach allows the ARGOS system to scale up in multiple levels and in many ways. On the hardware level we are able to add more processing power, memory, storage, or networking capabilities to meet growing demands. Vertical scaling of the ARGOS archiving and alerting subsystem, may be performed by adding more resources to a single machine, such as upgrading the CPU, adding more RAM, or increasing storage capacity. Horizontal scaling, may be performed by adding more processing nodes and joining them to the Proxmox cluster running bare-metal hypervisors. Moreover, on the virtualization level, we are able to increase accordingly the number of Virtual Machines and containers or upgrade existing ones to exploit increased capacity of hardware components multiplying their resources and capabilities in the platform

infrastructure. New Virtual Machines, run on new or upgraded hardware, enable the addition of more Kubernetes nodes to the cluster which translates to more processing power, memory and storage capacity for the platform's services. Kubernetes has the ability to automatically scale the number of application replicas based on observed CPU utilization or other configurable metrics. Also, it handles efficiently an increasing number of workloads, nodes, and clusters allowing applications to handle varying loads without manual intervention. Summing up, ARGOS's multi-level clustered approach provides easy scalability which allows the system to handle spikes in demand seamlessly, ensuring that performance remains consistent and user experience is not compromised.

Monitoring

Monitoring a cluster, especially in environments like Proxmox, Kubernetes, or other clustered systems, is crucial for several reasons. Effective monitoring ensures that you can maintain the performance, stability, and security of your cluster. Monitoring provides insights into CPU, memory, disk, and network usage which helps in understanding how resources are consumed across the cluster. Additionally, it assists in fault tolerance and efficient troubleshooting alerting administrators to potential problems like high CPU usage, memory leaks or network bottlenecks before they affect performance or cause downtime. On our multi-level clustered architecture two modern tools that visualize and monitor the status of the core components of the platform, Prometheus and Grafana, shall be deployed. Prometheus is an open-source systems monitoring and alerting toolkit that can scrape data from various sources such as Proxmox and Kubernetes and store them in its local time-series database. Prometheus is widely used for monitoring and alerting due to its reliability, powerful querying language, and ease of integration. Grafana is a web-based visualization tool that queries the metrics stored in Prometheus using Prometheus Query Language (PromQL) and creates custom, detailed and interactive dashboards for all kinds of possible metrics about our platform components. Grafana dashboards are composed of multiple panels, each representing a different set of data visualizations. These can include line graphs, bar charts, heatmaps, and other visualization charts. Finally, we highlight the fact that the above monitoring tools should not be deployed on the same virtual nodes that ARGOS alert and archiving subsystem runs.

5. Hardware Infrastructure

The architecture described in the previous section may rely on different types of computing, storage, and networking hardware. Typical clusters (server cluster refers to a collection of servers that work together under common orchestration to provide a greater level of availability, redundancy, and scalability) follow three different topologies, non-converged, converged, and hyper-converged. These three topologies are differentiated essentially by the storage pool placement and access/network fabric.

Although non-converged topology has many advantages and the best performance for most use cases, it also has one major drawback; the highest cost. Especially for small scale installations, the cost difference is substantial.

On the other hand, the hyper-converged topology has the lowest cost via the integration of computing and storage elements. Beyond the cost, there are other significant advantages but with the drawback of higher complexity, both for deployment and management of the cluster.

Hyper-converged infrastructure (HCI) is a data center technology paradigm that aims to reduce infrastructure complexity, enhance scalability and enable a truly software-defined IT infrastructure environment. HCI unifies computing, storage, networking and software into a single distributed infrastructure platform with intelligent distributed software minimizing data center complexity and increasing scalability. More specifically, its true power lies in the efficient combination of commodity data center server hardware with locally attached storage devices and the use of the aforementioned distributed software eliminating common single point of failures associated with legacy infrastructure. Traditional setups often rely on single, physical servers, so if server fails, due to hard drives, power supplies or other physical components, all the

applications and services running on it are affected, leading to significant downtime and causing the entire system to become inoperative until repairs are made.

Computing Nodes/Fabric

Although the computing power required for archiving and alerting is not on par with the requirements of the raw data and science processing; in order to be future proof and uniform, similar specifications should be used for the archiving nodes.

Therefore, the computing nodes should be built based on the following:

- the two latest generations of CPUs should be considered (i.e. for the year 2024: AMD EPYC 4th/5th Generation Processors, 4th/5th Gen Intel Xeon Scalable Processors)
- large cache sizes are advantageous
- a higher frequency CPU over a high core count one is preferable as there are still services that require high single thread performance
- CPU's number of PCIe lanes should be enough to directly support all the GPUs, NICs, NVMe SSDs, etc.
- support for DDR5 RDIMMs RAM or better technology if available in the future
- multi-CPU nodes typically offer better price - performance - consumption - rack requirements balance

Moreover, provision for high performance GPUs should be established. A well-balanced node should have at least as many GPUs as the CPUs number. The GPUs should be distributed across the CPUs for better NUMA system utilization and proper CPU affinity.

Network interfaces (NICs) should include at minimum 100 GbE with at least two ports per CPU. This will provide enough network capacity for both computing and storage transactions. The interfaces should be QSFP28 or QSFP56 for maximum flexibility. Again, for better NUMA system utilization and proper CPU affinity, the NICs should be distributed across the CPUs.

Networking Nodes/Fabric

The networking infrastructure could be based on Ethernet technologies. Ethernet is ubiquitous, proven in time and has an excellent value for money. Although there are technologies, i.e. InfiniBand, that provide some significant advantages over Ethernet, e.g. max throughput, latency, CPU offloading, etc., their cost, complexity, and inferior performance while using TCP/IP (via IPoIB) do impede their adaptation.

Currently, Ethernet's latest approved standard - 800 GbE - provides 800 Gbps of data rate. 200-GbE, 400-GbE, and even 800-GbE networking equipment is commercially available and 100 GbE is well established in data-center environments. 100 GbE provides a good price-performance ratio and can support the requirements of the ARGOS archiving and alerting cluster.

Storage Nodes/Fabric

Storage used to be the case of specialized nodes equipped with dedicated hardware with multiple drive bays and RAID controllers. Although the basic hardware that storage nodes are comprised of is essentially the same as that of the computing nodes, for marketing, historical, and management reasons storage nodes are considered as a different entity.

This separation, especially some years ago, also required a dedicated and specialized network infrastructure for the connectivity of computing and storage nodes. However, the performance evolution of the networking standards compared to the typical magnetic hard disk drive (HDD) based storage evolution has been massive. The solid-state drives (SSD) on the other hand, although they have evolved significantly in performance and capacity, they still cannot match the cost per capacity unit of an HDD. Therefore, the

storage capacity per drive, thus the capacity per node, may have increased, but the achievable throughput and input/output operations per second (IOPS) have not improved accordingly - at least when maximization of the capacity is the primary consideration.

Dedicated storage fabric is described by the architecture being incorporated as (a) Direct Attached Storage (DAS), (b) Network Attached Storage (NAS), and (c) Storage Area Network (SAN). The similarities of a typical SAN to the distributed storage of a hyper-converged topology are obvious. By using the computing nodes storage as a virtualized distributed storage, the only thing that differentiates from the SAN architecture is the dedicated network infrastructure. This is also achievable, and by sacrificing a small percentage of the performance, typical Ethernet based components may be used instead of InfiniBand or Fibre Channel ones.

6. Provision for Data Spaces

Data Space is a generic term that incorporates multiple closely coupled terms which are relative to common data usage in cooperative environments. By the definition provided by the EC, *Data Space is a framework that supports data sharing within a data ecosystem. It provides a clear structure for participants to share, trade, and collaborate on data assets in a way that is compliant with relevant laws and regulations and ensures fair treatment for all involved.* Data Spaces will empower the sharing, discovery, and use of distributed data within and across different sectors. It is the next step in order to provide ease of discovery and access, and at the same time preserve distributed storage and sovereignty over similar but dispersed big data. The European strategy for data is pushing towards the creation of a strong European Data Spaces ecosystem, and this may also include data created by astronomical observations. Data Spaces may offer a unification of the way data from diverse sources are discovered and accessed, without the need of replication and data pooling. Essentially, they provide a federated, open infrastructure for sovereign data sharing/exchange based on common policies, rules, and standards

A Data Space for astronomical data would be based on the following:

- Several astronomical facilities deployed in distributed sites
- Storage/archiving of data on local premises (at each site) forming federated data catalogs/datasets
- Each participant (facility) is the producer of astronomical data captured at the local site and possibly a consumer of astronomical data captured at other sites
- The data space architecture offers a trusted and streamlined environment for the data exchange between the facilities
- Access and usage policies are applied on data exchange/sharing, which ensures the data sovereignty of data producers

In order to be able to support a future observatory data space the following should be supported; (a) interoperability, (b) security, privacy, and trust, and (c) scalability and agility. There are several architectures that have been proposed and some partially implemented. International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), a non-profit organization focusing on establishing and promoting standards for data spaces, has produced the International Data Spaces Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM), as depicted in Figure 5. IDS-RAM is one of the already developed Data Space architectures that clearly shows the interactions between the components, along with the producers and consumers of data.

Figure 5: International Data Space Association (IDSA) Reference Architecture Model (RAM)

In order to support any kind of Data Space the key components needed are a metadata broker, a connector, and a data scheme/API. The main component that is missing from the ARGOS Archiving and Alerts subsystem services architecture, with a view to a Data Space architecture, is the connector. Therefore, a connector implementation will be designed and described, along with the requirements from the rest of the components, in order to be ready to transition to a future data space environment with minimum effort.

7. Conclusions

Summary

The archiving and alerts subsystem design is based on well-established components and technologies, exploiting all the virtualization capabilities provided by modern hardware and the respective software advancements. Redundancy, availability, scalability, and balancing, are essential and directly supported by the virtualization scheme proposed. Based on open-source software and typical COTS hardware a robust system can be build and provide the performance and expandability required.

Future Work

An initial minimal setup of the proposed architecture will be developed in a similar infrastructure in order to benchmark its subsystems, prepare the software images for easy deployment, and fine-tune the parameters of the software components. Moreover, we will actively pursue the development of a data space for observatories, providing a minimum viable subset for it.

8. References

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